

The Nansen-Bangladesh International Centre for Coastal, Ocean and Climate Studies

NABIC International Winter School 2014

***Coastal and ocean processes in the Bay of Bengal in a
changing climate and their impacts on society***

Scientific Student Report

Authors:

Abu Hena Muhammad Yousuf, Ahmed Tahmid Raihan, Md. Ahsanul Islam, Faiz Ahmad, Md. Fazlay Arafat, Gazi Azizul Islam, Jabir Thajudeen, Jannatul Feerdaus, Kishwar Jahan Chowdhury, Muhammad Golam Mustafa, Mahedi Hassan, Mahfjuz Rahman, Md. Mostafa Monwar, Md. Sohel Parvez, Md. Syful Islam, Md. Tarikul Islam, Md. Wahidul Alam, Md. Zakaria, Muhammad Shafeeque, Nabir Mammun, Nayan Mallick, Sabrina Nur, Sachin Pavithran A.P, Sarwar Jahan Chowdhury, Mohammad Saydul Islam Sarkar, Sayeda Umme Habiba, Shanta Soheli Moyna, Mir Shariful Islam, Zakia Sultana

Editors:

Lasse H. Pettersson, Md Abu Syed

Organized by:

Bangladesh Centre
for Advanced
Studies, Dhaka,
Bangladesh

Nansen-Bangladesh International Centre for
Coastal, Ocean and Climate Studies, Dhaka,
Bangladesh

Nansen
Scientific
Society

Nansen Scientific
Society, Bergen,
Norway

Nansen Environmental and
Remote Sensing Center,
Bergen, Norway

Sponsored by:

The Research Council
of Norway

Nansen
Scientific
Society

Dhaka/Bergen, 21 January 2015

Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

Thormøhlensgate 47

N-5006 Bergen - NORWAY

Phone: +47 55 20 58 00 Fax. +47 55 20 58 01

E-mail: administrasjon@nersc.no <http://www.nersc.no>

*a non-profit environmental research center
affiliated with the university of Bergen*

REPORT

TITLE NABIC International Research School 2014: <i>Coastal and ocean processes in the Bay of Bengal in a changing climate and their impacts on society – Scientific Student Report.</i>	REPORT No. NERSC technical report no. 344
CLIENT Research Council of Norway, Oslo	CONTRACT Project no 244822 (MILUTV)
CONTACT PERSONS Kristin Aasmundsen (DIV-INT)	AVAILABILITY OPEN
AUTHORS Editors: Lasse H. Pettersson and Md Abu Syed	DATE December 30. 2014
APPROVAL <i>Lasse H. Pettersson</i>	 <i>Stein Sandven, Director</i>

The NABIC International Winter Research School 2014

The NABIC International Winter Research School 2014 on “*Coastal and ocean processes in the Bay of Bengal in a changing climate and their impacts on society*” was held during October 12 to October 17, 2014 in Cox’s Bazar Bangladesh. The winter research school had a multi and cross-disciplinary thematic approach to understand research issues, challenges and opportunities in the Bay of Bengal region. 12 lecturers from Bangladesh, India and Norway during the event addressed research related to the Bay of Bengal and its implications on the society in Bangladesh. The event brought together interdisciplinary group of graduate students with background and/or interest in ocean dynamics, climate impacts and socio-political dimensions of climate change. This scientific report presents an overview of what were discussed, learned and highlights the issues research issues, challenges and opportunities in a changing climate scenarios in the Bay of Bengal region. The report is edited based on the contributions form the four student workinggroups formed during the winter school.

The participants of the NABIC International Winter Research School 2014 on “Coastal and ocean processes in the Bay of Bengal in a changing climate and their impacts on society”, October 12 to October 17, 2014 in Cox’s Bazar, Bangladesh.

Scientific Committee

Co-Chairmen:

- Dr. Atiq Rahman, Bangladesh Centre for Advanced Studies, Dhaka, Bangladesh, atiq.rahman@bcas.net
- Prof. Ola M. Johannessen, Nansen Scientific Society, Bergen, Norway, ola.johannessen@nersc.no

Members:

- Md Abu Syed, Bangladesh Centre for Advanced Studies, Dhaka, Bangladesh, abu.syed@bcas.net
- Lasse H. Pettersson, Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center, Bergen, Norway, lasse.pettersson@nersc.no

Organizing Committee

Co-chairmen:

- Md Abu Syed, Bangladesh Centre for Advanced Studies, Dhaka, Bangladesh, abu.syed@bcas.net
- Lasse H. Pettersson, Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center, Bergen, Norway, lasse.pettersson@nersc.no

Members:

- Bente E. Johannessen, Nansen Scientific Society, Bergen, Norway, bente.johannessen@nersc.no
- M. Shahadat Hossain, Institute of Marine Sciences and Fisheries, University of Chittagong, hossainms@yahoo.com

Table of Contents

Introduction	1
Climate, Oceanography and Storm Surge	3
Monsoon	3
Storm Surge	5
Facts about storm surges	5
Formulation of the model for storm surges in the Bay of Bengal.....	6
Sea Level Variations in Climate Change Scenario	7
Results of NABIC Winter School group exercise on sea level rise by the end of the 21st century for Cox’s Bazar, Bangladesh	10
Marine Ecosystem and Fisheries of Bay of Bengal.....	11
The Marine and Coastal Ecosystem.....	12
Coastal Configuration	12
Physico-chemical Conditions.....	12
Habitat diversity	13
Biological Environment/Food web/Food Chain	13
Fishery Resources and Activities.....	14
Fishery Resource Base	14
Fish Stock (Pelagic/Demersal/Fin-fish/Shell Fish).....	15
Catch/Production status.....	16
Climatic Variability and Fisheries and Ecosystem of BOB.....	17
Issues and Way Forward after NABIC Winter Schooling:.....	18
Coastal Zone Management in Bangladesh	18
Coastal zone of Bangladesh:.....	18
Coastal Resources:	19
Coastal Issues:.....	20
Coastal zone management:	20
Coastal Greenbelt:.....	20
Salt production	21
Salinity intrusion:	22
Water logging:.....	22
Pollution Control.....	22
Climate Change.....	23
Agriculture	23
Protection of Mangrove Forests:.....	23
Livestock.....	24
Afforestation.....	24

Water	24
Aquaculture	25
Tourism	25
Habitat Degradation and Migration.....	25
Sustainable management of natural resources	26
Societal Impacts and Governance.....	26
Major impacts of climate change on the coastal.....	26
Biotic Stress:.....	27
Agriculture:	27
Health	27
Tourism	27
Abiotic Stress:.....	28
Frequent Natural Disaster.....	28
Monsoon flooding	28
Reduction of Agriculture Land	28
Decline in Soil Quality.....	28
Species Disappearing	29
Coastal Erosion	29
Water Logging.....	29
Socio-Economic Impact of Sea Level Rise	29
Unemployment.....	30
Infrastructure Destruction	30
Emergence of Climate Refugee.....	30
High Cost of Natural Disasters.....	30
Loss of GDP and Emergence of Macroeconomic Tension	31
Risk on Education System.....	31
Appearance of Climate Poverty	31
High Economic Cost of Loosing Natural Resources	31
Diminution of Social Welfare	32
Future Impacts and Vulnerabilities Due to Climate Change	32
Adaptation Measures to mitigate the impacts of climate change	33
Agriculture sector.....	34
Housing and settlement	34
Rivers	35
Awareness raising and capacity building.....	35
Recommendations for Policy Makers.....	35
Central government.....	35
Coastal and river zones	36
Agricultural and fishery policy and extension support	36

Conclusion	37
References	38

Abbreviation

BOB	The Bay of Bengal
CEP	Coastal Embankment Project
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
DAE	Department of Agricultural Extension
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DO	Dissolved Oxygen
DoF	Department of Fisheries
EEZ	Exclusive Economic Zone
EIO	Equatorial Indian Ocean
ENSO	El Nino Southern Oscillation
FRSS	Fisheries Resource Survey System
FSYB	Fisheries Statistical Yearbook of Bangladesh
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GIA	Glacial Isotactic Adjustment
GIS	Geographical Information System
GMB	Ganges-Meghna-Brahmaputra
GMT	Generic Mapping Tool
ICZM	Integrated Coastal Zone Management
IOD	Indian Ocean Dipole
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IWRM	Integrated water resource management
LME	Large Marine Ecosystem
MSY	Maximum Sustainable Yields
NABIC	Nansen-Bangladesh International Centre for Coastal, Ocean and Climate Studies
NAPA	National Adaptation Program of Action
NGO	Non-government Organization
SLR	Sea-Level Rise
SST	Sea surface temperature
ST	Standing stock
TRM	Tidal River Management
WB	World Bank

Introduction

The Bay of Bengal (Figure - 1) a northern extended arm of the Indian Ocean is the largest bay in the world by area, which covers about 2,172,000 square kilometers. Many major rivers of India and Bangladesh flow into the Bay of Bengal: in the north, the Padma (distributaries of Ganges), Meghna and Brahmaputra River, and in the south Mahanadi River through the Mahanadi River Delta, Godavari River, Krishna River, Irrawaddy and Kaveri River. The Sundarbans mangrove forest is formed at the delta of the Ganges, Brahmaputra and Meghna rivers on the Bay of Bengal. Although the geographical setting of The Bay of Bengal is similar to The Arabian Sea, it is widely different from the Arabian Sea in terms of physical, chemical, and biological features (Brown, 2005). At the same time, The Bay of Bengal is characteristically different from the other tropical basins of the world primarily due to the huge amount of freshwater runoff and the associated sediment load (billions of tones) it brings into the basin (Kumar et al., 2006).

Figure 1: The Bay of Bengal.

One important meteorological feature of The Bay of Bengal is that it is characterized by the cyclic wind systems. The current patterns associated with these reversing wind systems and enormous river runoff influence the hydrographic parameters (Varadachari et al., 1968). The seasonal variation of regional climatic condition dominated by the monsoon system influences the physical, chemical and biological properties of the water of the Bay of Bengal, particularly the upper layer at the head of the Bay. The large river discharge during monsoon and reverse during the winter greatly control the water temperature, density, ocean current, salinity and their extents in the Bay. Variation of monsoon on set has significant impact on the climatic

events and crop production and vegetation cover in the region which has again influence in livelihoods of the people. Another important physical process is the tropical storm induced cyclone. The warm Bay of Bengal is a breeding ground for tropical cyclones. Tropical cyclones occur quite often with sever intensity in the Bay of Bengal during pre-monsoon and post monsoon and are accompanied with very strong wind and high storm surges.

The Bay of Bengal serves a vital role in a variety of functions for coastal and marine ecosystem. The coastal environment of BOB region plays a vital role in the nation's economy by virtue of its resources, productive habitats and rich biodiversity. Common problems of this Large Marine Ecosystem (LME) are unsustainable harvesting, habitat degradation, coastal pollution, and densely populated poor people heavily dependent of coastal and marine resources.

Coastal zone management is very important for Bangladesh since coastal population is around one-fourth of the country' population. The coastal zone has diverse livelihood activities that are vulnerable to water related natural hazards, and also affected by man-made hazards.

However, the local communities have been utilizing the coastal resources, without proper understanding of the ecosystem, policy plan and decisions. This resulted in complete destruction of some of important ecosystems. For instance Chakaria Sunderban mangrove forest had been replaced by donor driven (Asian Development Bank (ADB) and World Bank (WB) finance) aquaculture and shrimp farming project. The destruction of natural habitats in the form of reclamation of wetlands, cutting of mangroves and dumping of industrial and urban wastes worsens the plight of the coastal communities.

Vulnerabilities in the coastal zone of Bangladesh are increasing with accentuations of natural hazards and sea level rise caused by various factors. Proper governance need to be implemented to lessen the sufferings of the people, victim of climate change.

The bay obtain increased international attention due to the changes in its oceanographic and ecosystem dynamics as well as the exploitation of its natural resources that opens up for new challenges. Adequate scientific information to understand various processes with fine resolution both in coastal and deep-sea regions and trained manpower in physical, chemical and geological oceanography those required for managing marine resources sustainably and to cope with climate change induced hazards and vulnerability in the region particularly in the context of Bangladesh. To address these Nansen-Bangladesh International Centre for Coastal, Ocean and Climate Studies (NABIC) in collaboration with partners organized a winter research school on "Coastal and ocean processes in the Bay of Bengal in a changing climate, and their impacts on society" in October 2014. Participants were divided into 4 groups with 7-8 members in each group and they were assigned with following four research themes for their group exercises, intra and inter group collaborative works:

Group –I: Climate, Oceanography and Storm Surge

Group – II: Marine Fisheries

- Group – III: Coastal Zone Management
- Group – IV: Societal Impacts and Governance

Climate, Oceanography and Storm Surge

Monsoon

Monsoon is a seasonal prevailing wind in the South and Southeast Asian region, blowing from the southwest between May and September and bringing rain (the *wet monsoon*), or from the northeast between October and April (the *dry monsoon*).

WICC - West India Coastal Current
 EICC - East India Coastal Current
 LL - Lakshadweep low
 LH - Lakshadweep high
 SMC - Summer Monsoon Current
 WMC - Winter Monsoon Current

SEC - South Equatorial Current
 SECC - South Equatorial Counter Current
 EC - Equatorial Current
 EACC - East African Coastal Current
 SC - Somali Current

Figure 2: Schematic representation of major surface currents showing reversal of currents in the northern Indian Ocean during monsoon (source: Shankar et al., 2002)

An accurate forecast of seasonal summer monsoon rainfall over the country is an increasing demand for decision makers and planners of the monsoon affecting country in mitigating any kind of extreme events and disasters. The monsoon is known to exhibit a false or bogus monsoon onset in some years associated with propagating tropical intra-seasonal disturbances (Flatau et al., 2001). The bogus onset is characterized by enhanced convection and westerly surface winds similar to those that occur during monsoon onset but lasting a week or less. Often, bogus onsets are followed immediately by extended periods of weak winds and clear skies that result in heat waves and droughts in India. As bogus onsets can predate the actual onset by up to several weeks, it is particularly important for any onset determination to be insensitive to their occurrence.

Sea surface temperature (SST) anomalies on either side of the equator in Indian and Pacific oceans are found related to the date of monsoon onset over Kerala (India). Droughts in the June to September monsoon rainfall of India are followed by warm SST anomalies over tropical Indian Ocean and cold SST anomalies over west Pacific Ocean (Joseph, 2014).

The date of onset of southwest monsoon over Kerala, is a crucial date for India as it marks the beginning of a four month (June - September) period of rains in which contributes over 70% of its annual rainfall (Joseph, 2014).

Monsoon onset started in from 19th May to 20th June in the last 52 years monsoon but mostly in June and withdrawal occurred from 12th August – 27th September in India (Fasullo, and Webster, 2003). Monsoon withdrawal experiences a positive correlation with overall seasonal rainfall indicating that a delayed (early) withdrawal is associated with a stronger (weaker) monsoon season. Warm SST persists until a strong monsoon (Sadhuram et al. 2007) starts. SST directly influences the monsoon through evaporation and moisture supply into the system. Monsoon has an important intra-seasonal variability called active–break cycle of period varying 30-60 days. During active cycle there is an east–west band of raining convective clouds passing through India in the latitude belt 10_N–20_N from longitude 70_E extending beyond 120_E and the associated LLJ is located just south of this cloud band from central Arabian sea through peninsular India and the BoB to the west Pacific ocean.

The impact of monsoon on the local weather has different influences in different regions in Bangladesh. Though agriculture has been mechanized in last two decades still heavily rely on rain water for sowing and other irrigation. Hence, any changes in monsoon system and its associated precipitation have great influence in agriculture and aquaculture in Bangladesh. The south-west monsoon, active during June–September, which is also known as the summer monsoon, is an important source of water for Bangladesh and about 65–70% of the annual rainfall occur this season (Rahman, 2006). There is smaller process in the North Eastern part of Bangladesh which causes an earlier onset of monsoon and associated rainfall in the region (Reeve et al., 2014). This sometimes causes severe flashflood and damages crops and livelihoods.

Figure 3: Storm Surge phenomena in shallow and deep water

Storm Surge

Storm surges are oscillation of the water level in a coastal body of water in the time range of a few minutes to few days, resulting from the combination of very low barometric pressure in the storm center (the inverse barometer), winds directed in the direction of storm movement and the physical geography of a coastline (Gönnert et al., 2001). Heavy winds produced by cyclones push the ocean in front of them. As this water get pushed into the shallow zones along the coastline, sea level rises. Since the storm surge is driven by the winds, the rise in sea level is related to the velocity of the wind. For a moving storm the greater winds occur on the right side of the storm (in the northern hemisphere) (Storch, 2012). Sea level also rises beneath the eye of the storm due to the low pressure in the eye. But, the surge generated by this low pressure is usually much less than the wind-driven surge. The height of the storm surge depends on wind speed, the shape of the coastline, and variations in the water depth along the coast line. Height also depends on tidal cycles. If a storm approaches the coast during high tide, the storm surge will be higher than if it approaches during low tide (Hassan, 2005).

Facts about storm surges

Though Storm surge is sudden and substantial rise in sea level above normal astronomical tide due to fierce winds and pressure drops associated with cyclones but this include some facts also. It is a long Gravity Wave where the wave speed is denoted by $V = \sqrt{gh}$ which is a shallow water problem. Storm surge may last for a few hours to a few days, depending upon the speed of the cyclone. Maximum surge normally reaches at the time of the landfall of the cyclone. The more intense is the storm, the stronger is the wave. If the occurrence of storm surge coincides with normal astronomical tide the total rise in the water level may be spectacular. If Sea Level Rise (SLR) occurs then amplitude of storm surges will reduce as the shallow water problem (Debsarma, 2009).

Figure 4: Jul-Aug 850 hPa wind for the period 1951 to 2009 showing the cross

The Bay of Bengal is frequently affected by storm surges associated with tropical cyclones. They may last from a few minutes to several days, depending on the cyclone's size and speed of movement. Eighty percent of the global casualties due to storm surges occur in Bangladesh

because of the complex coastal geometry of the Bay of Bengal's northern tip. Maximum surge found in the super cyclone Sidr was about 6.04 m (Sarkar, 2012).

Of all the countries surrounding the Bay of Bengal, Bangladesh suffers most from storm surges. The main factors contributing to disastrous surges in Bangladesh may be summarized as shallow coastal water, convergence of the bay, high astronomical tides, thickly populated low-lying islands, favorable cyclone track, and innumerable number of inlets including world's largest river system Ganga–Brahmaputra–Meghna (Ali 1979).

Formulation of the model for storm surges in the Bay of Bengal

IIT Storm Surge Model is a vertically integrated semi-implicit forward with time numerical storm surge model. A Linux/Windows based high resolution numerical/hydro-dynamical storm surge model is developed by the author based on the IIT model and air-bubble is entrained in

Figure 5: Air-Bubble entrainment and simulation of Aila surge. (Sarkar, 2012).

2009. Dr. Azizur Rahman used this model in his PhD research titled “Effects of Air-Bubbles on Storm Surge” in 2011. This model has been used to simulate storm surge scenarios might have caused by severe cyclones like Sidr-2007 etc. 2-D and 3-D storm surge scenarios were created for several storms. Visualization is made by using GMT (Generic Mapping Tool). The basic hydrodynamic equations of continuity and momentum for the dynamical process in the sea in flux form, after neglecting barometric forcing, may be given by Equation of continuity:

$$\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \tilde{u}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial y} = 0 \dots (i)$$

Horizontal Momentum equation,

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{u}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial (u\tilde{u})}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial (v\tilde{u})}{\partial y} - f\tilde{v} = -g(\zeta + h) \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial x} + \frac{F_s}{\rho} - \frac{C_f \tilde{u} \sqrt{u^2 - v^2}}{(\zeta + h)} \dots (ii)$$

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial (u\tilde{v})}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial (v\tilde{v})}{\partial y} + f\tilde{u} = -g(\zeta + h) \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial y} + \frac{G_s}{\rho} - \frac{C_f \tilde{v} \sqrt{u^2 - v^2}}{(\zeta + h)} \dots (iii)$$

Where, $\tilde{u} = (\zeta + h) u$ and $\tilde{v} = (\zeta + h) v$ are prognostic variables and $(\zeta+h)$ gives the total depth of the basin. $f=2\Omega\sin\Phi$ (Coriolis parameter) (Debsarma 2009).

Required meteorological and hydrological inputs are vector motion of the storm (centre), radius of maximum wind, pressure drop and topographic & bathymetric data (ETOPO2).

Figure 6: 3D Simulation of Surge due to Sidr-2007

Figure 7: IIT Surge Model Product: 15-19 May 1997 Cyclone (Debsarma 2009)

Figure 8: Simulated peak surge contours (m) for the 2007 Sidr cyclone (Dube 2009)

Sea Level Variations in Climate Change Scenario

There are major causes of global sea level rise are thermal expansion of the oceans (water expands as it warms) and the loss of land-based ice due to increased melting (IPCC, 2007). Also global warming is the main contributor to the rise in sea level since the industrial Revolution. Human activities such as burning coal and oil and cutting down tropical forests increase atmospheric concentrations of heat-trapping gases. The rate of sea-level rise (SLR) has accelerated since 1990, approximately doubling, as numerous reports state, with the greatest portion of rise occurring in the southern hemisphere. However, sea level did not rise uniformly everywhere; in fact, it actually declined in some broad areas. Thus, the pattern of sea level change is complex. This is primarily due to the fact that winds, ocean currents,

Figure 9: Regional Sea level Trends from satellite altimetry for the period of October 1992 to July 2009 (Nicholls and Cazenave 2010).

continental runoff, salinity, gravity and such other factors like isostatic adjustment affect sea level, and these too are changing concurrently.

Recent studies using satellite altimetry data suggest that sea level rise by about 2.39 ± 0.48 mm/yr between 2005 and 2011 (J.L Chen et al., 2013). The Argo data indicate a density-driven sea level rise of 0.60 ± 0.27 mm/yr throughout this period. A reassessment suggests ocean mass contribution of 1.80 ± 0.47 mm/yr, for a total sea level rise of 2.40 ± 0.54 mm/yr, in agreement with the altimeter-based estimates. Also for the period 2003 to 2009 found glacier outside of Greenland and Antarctic ice sheets has lost about 259 trillion Kg/yr for the last six years which will contribute to 0.7mm/yr rise in sea level (Gardner et al., 2013). Current estimates predicts that the entire ice of Antarctic, Greenland and all other world glaciers can rise global sea level by 60m, 6m and 60cm respectively.

Current changes in the ocean around Antarctica are disturbingly close to conditions 14,000

years ago research led to the Antarctic abrupt 3- global found when

that new shows may have rapid melting of ice and an 4 metre rise in sea level. It is that in the past, ocean

temperatures around Antarctica became more layered with a warm layer of water below a cold surface layer ice sheets and glaciers melted much faster than when the cool and warm layers mixed more easily. This defined layering of temperatures is exactly what is happening now around the Antarctic (Nature Communications, 2014a). Land-ice decay at the end of the last five ice-ages caused global sea-levels to rise at rates of up to 5.5 metres per century, according to a new study. Researchers developed a 500,000 year record of sea-level variability, to provide the first account of how quickly sea-level changed during the last five ice-age cycles. Scientists also found that more than 100 smaller events of sea-level rise took place in between the five major events.

Figure 10: Time series of global mean sea level from 1800 to 2100 (deviation from the 1980-1999 mean) in the past and as projected for the future.

The really fast rates of sea-level rise typically seem to have happened at the end of periods with exceptionally large ice sheets, when there was two or more times more ice on the Earth than today (Nature Communications, 2014b). Figure 1 represents the time series of global mean sea level in the past and as projected for the future (IPCC, 2007).

What causes the sea to rise is when all the water that is now frozen as ice and lies on land melts and flows into the sea. It is first and foremost about the two large, kilometre- thick ice sheets on Greenland and Antarctica, but also mountain glaciers. In addition, large amounts of groundwater is pumped for both drinking water and agricultural use in many parts of the world and more groundwater is pumped than seeps back down into the ground, so this water also ends up in the oceans (Environmental Research Letters, 2014).

A new study of satellite data from the last 19 years reveals that fresh water from melting

Figure 11: Potential Sea Level Rise Contribution

glaciers has caused the sea level around the coast of Antarctica to rise by 2cm more than the global average of 6cm. Researchers detected the rapid rise in sea-level by studying satellite scans of a region that spans more than a million square kilometers. The melting of the Antarctic ice sheet and the thinning of floating ice shelves has contributed an excess of around 350 gigatonnes of freshwater to the surrounding ocean. This has led to a reduction in the salinity of the surrounding oceans that has been corroborated by ship-based studies of the water. Freshwater is less dense than salt water and so in regions where an excess of freshwater has accumulated we expect a localized rise in sea level.

The Indian Ocean is unique with a northern boundary located primarily in the tropics. To illustrate, in the presence of seasonally reversing monsoon, the Equatorial Indian Ocean (EIO) is subjected to distinct zonal oscillating [westerly and easterly] winds, which generate pairs of downwelling and upwelling Kelvin waves (Rao et al., 2010). The climatic modes which dominate the sea level variations in Bay of Bengal (BoB) are El Nino Southern Oscillation [ENSO] (Mc Phaden et al., 2006), the Indian Ocean Dipole [IOD] (Saji et al., 1999; Webster et al., 1999) and Madden Julian Oscillation [MJO] (Madden and Julian, 1972). Inter-annual sea level variations in the BoB are mainly identified due to ENSO and IOD and this is one of the regions, where strongest inter-annual variability occurs (Nidheesh et al., 2012). Studies by Aparna et al. (2012) using tide gauge and altimeter data show that IOD and ENSO leave a characteristic signature in BoB sea level which is not evident off west coast of India. Sea level variations in the eastern equatorial Indian Ocean and BoB are highly correlated too in both inter-annual (Rao et al., 2010) and decadal time scales (Nidheesh et al., 2012). Likewise, the variability of sea level in Arabian Sea is not well understood under the realm of changing global environments.

Results of NABIC Winter School group exercise on sea level rise by the end of the 21st century for Cox's Bazar, Bangladesh

The NABIC winter school 2014 on Coastal and ocean processes in the Bay of Bengal in a changing climate and their impacts on society was held in Cox's Bazar in Bangladesh from October 12 to 18, 2014. 30 graduate students from Bangladesh and India were for six days

gartered to learn, interact study the ocean and coastal processes in the Bay of Bengal under the present and future climate conditions and its impact on the society.

The following Chart represents the Results of NABIC Winter School group exercise on sea level rise by the end of the 21st century for Cox’s Bazar, Bangladesh

Table 1: Global patterns - Relative sea level (RSL) Change between 1986–2005 to 2081–2100 CMIP5 RCP4.5 at Cox’s Bazar, Bangladesh. Assessment by the student working groups at NABIC 2014.

Contributing factors	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Average	Percent
Mass from ice sheet	0.2	0.175	0.175	0.175	0.18	34
Mass from glaciers	0.125	0.125	0.15	0.125	0.13	25
Glacial Isotactic Adjustment	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025	0.025	5
Steric height (Thermal expansion)	0.21	0.2	0.18	0.21	0.20	37
Atmospheric Pressure	0	-0.0025	0	-0.005	-0.0019	0
Total estimated	0.56	0.52	0.53	0.53	0.54	100
Map Projection	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	

The following are the major findings –

- In case of ice sheet melting the maximum RSL is about 0.3 m globally. But in Cox-Bazar coast 0.18 m . This indicates that in the upcoming future the coast of Bangladesh is going to suffer a lot due to climate change.
- Glacier melt is a bit lower than ice sheet melting in Bangladesh coast.
- As we don’t have glaciers in Bangladesh so the effect of it is not that much alarming for us.
- We have longer summer and receive more heat from the sun and this causes huge thermal expansion in BOB, eventually this thermal expansion is highly responsible for most of the surge!
- We receive more heat and these make the atmosphere warm and crate a low pressure status in maximum case.

The result we have found is 50-54 cm projected see level rise by the end of the 21st century for Cox’s Bazar, Bangladesh. And this is very alarming for our coastal people and future generation.

Marine Ecosystem and Fisheries of Bay of Bengal

The Marine and Coastal Ecosystem

Coastal Configuration

From the geo-morphological point of view the coastal areas of five BOB countries are very diverse. The conditions in Bangladesh can be broadly divided into three distinct geomorphological regions (Hossain 2004); western (Sundarbans and adjacent areas), central (Most of the combined flow of the Ganges-Brahmaputra-Meghna system of low-lying area) and eastern (southern tip of the main land in Teknaf-Cox's Bazar) regions

Physico-chemical Conditions

The physico-chemical information on coastal and marine ecosystems in BOB countries is very scattered and limited. In Bangladesh part of coastal zone and EEZ, alternation of northeast and southeast monsoons brings about a complete reversal of the surface current pattern, which is clockwise from January to July and counter clockwise from August to December, according to the direction of the wind (Lamboeuf 1987). Velocity of current varies from 4.5 to 5.5 knots during spring tide in the summer monsoon, while in the neap tide it is 2.3 -3.9 knots (Lamboeuf 1987). The southwest monsoon, characterized by hot and humid winds blows from the Bay of Bengal during May-September, resulting heavy rainfall. The northeast monsoon blows during November-March bringing cool, dry air from the continental areas, and between the two monsoons, wind is variable and unstable causing frequent cyclones and tidal surges.

Salinity in Bangladesh coast during monsoon turns hypo-saline due to discharge by GBM river system. The highest sea surface temperature (SST) in Bangladesh EEZ is reportedly varied between 24.10C and 26.5 0C. The DO content decreases rapidly with depth. The pH ranges between 6.9 and 8.9. The concentrations of nitrate, phosphate and silicate vary from 0.16 to 8.98 $\mu\text{g-at/l}$, 0.08 to 2.33 $\mu\text{g-at/l}$ and 0.67 to 63.31 $\mu\text{g-at/l}$, respectively. Ship breaking industry is one of the most important sources of pollution and other land based industrial activities.

Summer upwelling along the east coast of India is weak due to simultaneous downwelling caused by Ekman pumping (wind driven) over the Bay of Bengal and remote forcing from the Equator (Shetye et al., 1991). Although upwelling and convective processes are reported to occur in Southwestern of the Bay of Bengal (Vinayachandran and Mathew, 2003) these are much weaker than in the Arabian Sea. Thus, the strengths of upwelling and convective processes in the Bay Bengal are not strong enough to force effective entrainment of properties between surface and subsurface waters. Eddies may supply nutrients to surface layers in the Bay (Prasannakumar et al., 2004) the quantitative significance of which is yet to be ascertained. The solar heat absorbed by the Bay of Bengal remains in the surface layers, without being transferred to deep waters, facilitating the development of atmospheric disturbances; i.e., low-pressure systems are more prominent and frequent over the Bay of Bengal than over the Arabian Sea. Occurrence of frequent atmospheric disturbances, due to

prevailing freshwater lens and low winds, results in more rainfall and subsequent river discharge that again promote disturbances; a system similar to a ‘do’ loop indicating positive feedback (Figure ...). Biogeochemical processes in the North Indian Ocean are driven by monsoons and hence it is apt to name the present subject as the ‘Monsoon biogeochemistry’.

Figure 12: Relation between low salinity lens (fresh water) at the surface of the bay and the atmospheric disturbance (storms, cyclones, etc.)

Habitat diversity

The coast line is endowed with a wide range of coastal ecosystems like mangroves, coral reefs, sea grasses, salt marshes, sand dunes, estuaries, lagoons and natural habitats. Sandy, muddy, stony and mangrove forested shorelines are found throughout coastal countries in BOB regions. Most remarkably along the parts of the coastline controlled by sediments and a long stretched beaches without fringing reefs. Some beach areas have high sandy dunes produced by wind-blown sand. These sands are carried and deposited by the river. Sand dunes support varieties of wild and often act as nesting facilities for sea turtle.

The coast of Bangladesh as a whole is characterized by soft substrate ecosystems. Elevation is gradual and sedimentary environment leads to growth of mangroves, sea grasses and algal beds. These are highly productive, nutrients-rich, and acts as feeding, breeding, nesting areas for many marine lives. The freshwater influxes through GBM system have significant influence on coastal environment of the BOB in Bangladesh area.

Biological Environment/Food web/Food Chain

The primary productivity of the Bay of Bengal is very high; 0.98 and 3.9 g C/m²/day. A total of 135 phytoplankton species identified. High conc. of zoo-plankton (250 species) was also found in the BOB. In overall, the east of the Bay is very rich ichthyo-diversity. Ecological

attributes of these include high biological productivity; provision of nutrients, feeding, breeding or nesting areas for marine and other animals. The ecosystem study of the BOB, nitrite, nitrate, silicate and phosphate were found to correlate positively with depth at all sampling stations. Like other tropical waters, the coastal and marine waters of Bangladesh are very rich in varieties of aquatic lives. A large number of species are exploited by any single type of fishing operation, but the catch compositions depends on the fishing grounds, fishing gears, fishing seasons, lunar period and tidal flow. Marine capture fisheries resources in Bangladesh are considered close to full exploitation in coastal region and under exploitation in deeper EEZ.

Figure 13: Relation between physical forcing and biological interactions (Svein Sundby, IMR, Norway).

Advection and spreading act to distribute the smaller organism, these processes also transport nutrient into the euphotic zone, thereby controlling where areas with high and low biological production in the ocean are found. Light is necessary for photosynthesis and many larger organism also organize their daily cycle after the availability of light. In high and mid-latitudes, availability of light controls the annual cycle of biological production. Most organisms have preferred a temperature range, if the temperature gets much warmer or colder than that they get stressed. Turbulence is often a stress on phytoplankton, both because it damages them and because it can transport them out of the euphotic zone where they can grow. For zooplankton, turbulence can also increase the encounter rate between organisms and therefore be beneficial for feeding and mating, but for small zooplankton turbulence can also be an environmental stress.

Fishery Resources and Activities

Fishery Resource Base

Bangladesh coastal and marine fisheries contribute about 17.84% of the total fish production (3.06 million tons) of the country. With an annual increase of 5.5% country produced 0.55 million ton in 2010-2011. Hilsa is the dominant species with production of 339845 ton in 2010-11. Hilsa being an anadromous species is caught in sea, estuary and in rivers during breeding season. Other major marine species commercially caught are catfishes, Bombay ducks, jaw-fish, ribbon fish, sardines, mackerels and conger eels etc. The total shrimp production was 152520 ton in 239460 t in 2010-11, while total marine shrimp catch was 31976 t and 56989 t in 2010-11 and 2010-11, respectively. Artisanal fishing lands more compared to industrial fishing in Bangladesh.

There are reported 475 fish species in Bangladesh waters of which 15-20 species contributes almost 75% of commercial landings. Among the fish groups, largest 68 species of sharks are available. There are 17 species of shrimps and five species of lobster in Bangladesh waters, 3 species of cephalopods have been recorded from the EEZ of BoB. Some species of marine turtles travel in the Bangladesh marine territory. Nineteen species of seaweeds are available in the Bangladesh coast.

Table 2: Fishery Resource Based in BOB

Resource type	Number	Resource type	Number
Fish	475	Seaweed	168
Shrimp	17	Sponge	3
Mollusk	336	Crab	16
Lobster	5	Dolphin	9
Turtle	5	Whale	3

(Source: Quader 2010)

Apart from this, there are five most abundant species in the Bay of Bengal (BoB) captured by number were in the following order skipjack tuna (*Katsuwonus pelamis*, 22.94%), swordfish (*Xiphias gladius*, 12.94%), silky shark (*Carcharhinus falsiformis*, 8.82%), frigate tuna (*Auxis thazard*, 8.24%) and bigeye thresher shark (*Alopias supersiliosus*, 6.47%) (BIMSTEC, 2007).

Fish Stock (Pelagic/Demersal/Fin-fish/Shell Fish)

Due to the lack of adequate information on the standing stocks of pelagic, mid layer resources and sustainable harvest, development of proper biological management policy on this sector has become impossible in most countries of the BOB region. Though it is reported that demersal stocks in different countries are somewhat measured.

In Bangladesh, it was estimated the standing stock of demersal fish is roughly 264,000–374,000 ton, and 9,000 ton shrimp. Some survey on shrimp, pelagic and demersal stock of fish was done excluding expanded EEZ of Bangladesh.

Period	Vessel	Trawl gear		Note
Nov-Dec 79	R V Dr. Fridtjof Nansen	Shrimp	49 Hauls	Abundance est. 160000 mt
May 80	R V Dr. Fridtjof Nansen	shrimp	61	Abundance est. 90000 mt
Sep 84- June 86	R V Anusandani	Engel type	544 hauls	Stock density 2914-7926 kg/km ²
Oct 88- April 89	R V Anusandani	Shrimp	83 hauls	Stock density 141 kg/km ² 51-80m
Jun 88- Jan 89	R V Machhranga	High opening engel type	31 hauls	Biomass in <20m 1700 t (fish) 135 t (shrimp)

Table 3: Some historic survey of Bay of Bengal for fisheries resource assessment.

However, these are not routine and conclusive. The scarce data on available harvestable resources (nearly 0.5 million ton/year) in Bangladesh is fraught with danger of over-fishing especially in coastal zones and territorial waters as artisanal fishing is extensively done.

Table 4: Standing stock (ST) of fish & shrimp of the Bay of Bengal

Demersal fish	Pelagic fish	Shrimp	Referred Authors
160,000	90,000-160,000	-	Saetre (1981)
200,000-250,000	160,000-200,000	4,000-6,000	Penn (1982)
152,000	-	-	Khan (1983)
-	-	3,300	White & Khan (1985)
188,000	25,600	-	Lamboeuf (1987)

Catch/Production status

Renewable resources needs to be exploited based on quantified stocks and without endangering resource base. Non-renewable resources should be utilized in such a manner that does not destroy habitat, ecosystem and with causing minimum possible pollution. Biotic renewable resources needs their exact stock quantified and scientific analysis to determine exploitable rates based on maximum sustainable yields (MSY) and recruitment possibilities under various conditions. Stock may be determined based on their habitat, dwellings and /or ecosystem. But better options should be species-wise so selective gears could be developed.

In Bangladesh the harvest is controlled by limiting the number of vessel to catch any specific species like shrimp and it is applicable only for trawlers, but not for artisanal fishing boat. The licensing of

new shrimp trawlers is stopped (capped) because of the heavy fishing pressure on the shrimp.

Figure 14: Generalized Productivity Trends in Bay of Bengal

To monitor the marine catch in Bangladesh, there is a system under the DoF, the Fisheries Resource Survey System (FRSS). The FRSS produce a Fisheries Statistical Yearbook of Bangladesh (FSYB) based on the annual catch monitoring.

Climatic Variability and Fisheries and Ecosystem of BOB

Climate change positively or negatively impacts way of lives of the coastal dwellers and specially fishing communities. The coastal ecosystem including intertidal zones, tidal fluctuations, mangroves, coral reefs all collectively affects climate and vice-versa. The coastal mangroves are disappearing at an alarming rate and that adversely affects breeding, spawning, nursing and feeding grounds for many marine lives and adversely affects biodiversity in the peripheral seas. The mangrove ecosystems, salt marshes and mud-flat services in terms of life supporting, provisioning and regulating functions and services and so has tremendous impacts on the climate change adaptation of coastal community. Main climate change adaptation programs thus comprised analyzing and developing appropriate value chains and conservation linked livelihood options.

The Bangladesh coast is frequently hit by natural calamities and climate change issues have adversely affects lives and livelihoods and slowed down the pace of social and economic developments in this region. Remote coastal localities are more affected during disasters and relief efforts. When rebuilding process initiate after the disaster, poor market access, credit and other services, institutional weaknesses and depleted resource base delay and hamper the recovery process.

Finally, it has been revealed that Integrated Coastal Zone Management (ICZM) is vital for judicious management of coastal flora and fauna and their exploitation by the coastal dwellers and the livelihoods of the coastal people. ICZM is the need of present day for responsible management of coastal resources of any country.

Current unsustainable harvesting of Hilsa and other species need to be done in a rational way with adequate scientific knowledge of Hilsha breeding area extent, movement pattern; Gravid mother of the tiger shrimp should be harvested rationally. There needs to be detailed resource quantification and mapping, Preservation of mangroves. Species-wise resource assessments, Complete Digital MCS; Research on resource assessment and digital mapping; Research on coastal aquaculture and mariculture.

Issues and Way Forward after NABIC Winter Schooling:

A. Fisheries Governance in Bay of Bengal

1. Stock Assessment Update
2. Fishing Zone Detection/ Advisory Services
3. Trans-boundary Species Monitoring

B. Addressing Climate Variability in Coastal and Ocean Process posing Fisheries System Anomalies

1. Migration Pattern Anomalies due to climate variability
2. Spawning pattern Anomalies due to climate variability
3. Coastal Fishers Livelihood threatening due to climate induced extreme events

Coastal Zone Management in Bangladesh

Coastal zone of Bangladesh:

Bangladesh coast, facing the Bay of Bengal in the South is 710 km long and the coastal zone covers an area of about 2.85 million hectares, which is 23 percent of the country's total area. Bangladesh has an area of 147,570 sq.km. with one-third of the country belonging to the coastal zone (Ministry of Water Resources, 2005). The population of coastal zone is approximately 35 million. The combined out-fall of the Ganges, the Brahmaputra and the Meghna that rank among major rivers of the world, discharges to the Bay of Bengal at the meeting point of east-west and north-south coastlines. Major part of the coastal zone is covered by the deltas of the Ganges and the Meghna where the coastline is oriented along

east-west direction. These regions are criss-crossed by a network of interconnected distributaries and estuaries. The other part is covered by the Chittagong coastal plain bordered by hills, and the coastline is oriented along north-south direction. (Choudhury, J.U. 2011)

The coastal zone contains many ecosystems, e.g. mangrove, marine, estuary, islands, coral and sandy beaches.

The coastal zone has a great importance since pre-historic times for its abundance in natural resources. Due to lack of appropriate guidelines for natural resource conservation and utilization, land use conflicts occur and the coastal zone turned into areas of major conflicts.

Figure 15: Coastal zone of Bangladesh

Coastal Resources:

The main coastal resources are as follows-

- Fisheries,
- Agricultural land,
- Forest,
- Mining,
- Tourism,
- Salt production,
- Sea-port facilities,
- Livestock,

- Port and Harbors, etc.

Shoreline protection:

1. Coastal erosion
2. Greenbelt
3. Marine drive road
4. Change in bottom topography
5. Water logging
6. Impacts of engineering structures
7. Deposition and sediment transportation.

Coastal water quality:

1. Salinity Intrusion
2. Agricultural run-off
3. Aquaculture development.
4. Oil pollution
5. Dumping
6. Ship breaking activities
7. Municipal waste
8. Industrial waste
9. Fluvial transport
10. Eutrophication

Coastal Hazards and water change:

1. Sea level rise
2. Cyclone and storm surge
3. Habitat degradation and migration
4. Flood
5. Emergency Response Team (Govt. and NGO)
6. Cyclone shelter
7. Salt production

Coastal Development:

1. Embankment
2. Coastal Tourism
3. Drainage
4. Land use zoning
5. Sustainable resource management
6. Development of ports and harbors'.
7. Urbanization
8. Aquaculture

Coastal Issues:

The followings are the coastal issues we have to consider for coastal zone management-

Coastal zone management:

Coastal Greenbelt:

A greenbelt defined as natural or artificially created coastal vegetation along the coast designed to prevent coastal erosion and mitigate the adverse impact of natural coastal hazards on human lives and property.

Repeated devastating cyclones and tidal surges led foresters to initiate the raising of mangrove trees on barren coastal areas in 1966. However, the local communities have been haphazardly utilizing the coastal resources, resulting in complete destruction of some of them e.g. Chakaria Sunderban mangrove forest (Hossain and Lin, 2001). Following are the coastal greenbelt management suggestion-

- a. Several design considerations needs to be taken across the landscape to reduce vulnerability from cyclonic winds. The design starts with sand dune followed by plantations in beach, roadside plantation or marine drive / embankment (where available), homestead plantation and hill plantation. The basic premise is to gradually redirect the flow of wind in the upward direction using bioengineering or natural infrastructure. That is creating a series of windbreaks of gradual heights against the follow of the wind.
- b. Shelterbelt orientation is another important factor to shelterbelt structure. The maximum shelter effectiveness is generally obtained when the shelter belt is oriented perpendicular to the wind direction. A checkerboard pattern is required when the winds originate from different directions (J-J Zhu 2008; FAO 1989).
- c. Site specific plant species, height, width, porosity and density of the greenbelt should be maintained in order to provide shelter to the coastal lives against cyclones, tsunami and tidal surges.

Salt production

In 1960, the Bangladesh Small and Cottage Industries Corporation started to produce salt on 2,742 hectares in Chittagong and Cox's Bazar districts in southeast of Bangladesh, where salt production continues to be concentrated. Since then, land use under salt production had been gradually increasing to meet the ever-growing demand. There are 41,000 listed salt producers. In 2003/2004, 0.9 million tonnes of salt were produced from 24,900 ha land (Ahmed, 2011).

However, the increasing trend of salt production has negative impact on our coastal environment as most of the salt production areas created through destroying mangrove forest. Moreover, these salt production areas make the land so saline that it failed to support any sorts of vegetation on its adjacent areas. Conversion of agriculture land to salt produced plot is another problem.

- a. Salt production areas should be restricted in some specific places adjacent to sea areas.
- b. Clearing of mangrove forest for salt production should be stopped immediately.
- c. There should be proper rules and regulations to manage the salt production.
- d. Environmental friendly techniques should introduce for salt production in the coastal areas.

Salinity intrusion:

Salinity intrusion is the movement of saline water into surface fresh water bodies, areas naturally used to non saline and underground aquifers, which can lead to contamination of drinking and household water sources accompanying other consequences. Due to salinity intrusion agriculture production is greatly hampered in the coastal region, coastal population experiencing switching to other livelihoods other than agricultural crop production. Along with these fisheries, livestock, mangrove forest ecosystem, fresh water availability is also facing tremendous problem. The problem becomes severe in dry season along the coastal areas.

Reduction of upstream fresh water flow, sea level rising, high spring tide inundation, cyclone and storm surges are the main reason of salinity intrusion in Bangladesh coastal areas.

Management strategy:

- a. Structural management:
 - Establishment of embankment, sluice gate, dams etc.
 - Freshwater flow counter balance
- b. Reclamation:
 - Reclamation of saline soil by drainage and salt leaching.

Water logging:

Coastal Embankment Project (CEP) implemented in 1960s to increase agricultural production, it irreversibly changed coastal region's ecosystems. These disconnected the wetlands from the rivers which created water logging in southwestern part of Bangladesh. Remaining salt water increased the salinity concentration of the soil.

Management strategy:

- a. Introduction of Integrated water resource management (IWRM) and ensure its implementation.
- b. Using GIS and Remote sensing technologies and Digital Elevation Model (DEM) to generate flood inundation map.
- c. Mathematical formulation has to be made to assess the rate of tidal sedimentation.
- d. Locality specific solution and field investigation should be done carefully.
- e. Evolving Tidal River Management (TRM) along the water logged region.

Pollution Control

Management strategy:

- a. Zoning regulations will be established for location of new industries in consideration of fresh and safe water availability and effluent discharge possibilities;

- b. All industrial units will be required to install built-in safeguards against pollution within a given timeframe.
- c. Sewage treatment plants will be set up for the major cities like Chittagong, Khulna and Barisal and gradually in other urban centers;
- d. Steps will be taken to handle the issue of discharge of bilge water from ships and oil-spill according to international conventions.
- e. Ship breaking industry should be regulated in an eco-friendly way.

Climate Change

Management strategy:

- a. Existing institutional arrangements for monitoring of climate change in Bangladesh will continue. Steps will be taken to support upgrading of technology and institutional strengthening for enhancing their capacity for generation of better data and more accurate long-term prediction and risk related to climate change;
- b. Implementation of adaptive measures identified in relation to climate change for coastal zone and resources shall be gradually undertaken;
- c. Efforts shall be made to continuously maintain sea-dykes along the coastline as first line of defense against predicted sea-level rise;
- d. An institutional framework for monitoring/detecting sea level rise shall be made along with a contingency plan for coping with its impact.

Agriculture

Management strategy:

- a. Programs for intensification of agriculture and crop diversification for improving the economic conditions of both male and female farmers and increasing food security at local and regional level shall be supported;
- b. Special development programs will be taken-up with a view to increasing the production of crops suitable for the coastal area with attention to maintenance of soil health;
- c. Use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides will be reduced, while organic manure and integrated pest management will be encouraged;
- d. Salt-tolerant crop varieties will be developed and extended along with possible measures to resist salinity;
- e. The scope of irrigation facilities will be explored and / or extended and a comprehensive water management for agriculture will be implemented.

Protection of Mangrove Forests:

Evergreen mangroves known as 'tidal forests' constitute a fascinating ecosystem. For centuries, this ecosystem has been of great use and value to mankind. It helps in preventing soil erosion, floods and other natural calamities; Mangroves' protective buffer zone helps shield coastlines from storm surges and wave action, minimizing damage to property and

losses of life from hurricanes and storms. Mangroves have been useful in treating effluent, as the plants absorb excess nitrates and phosphates, thereby preventing contamination of near-shore waters.

Mangroves absorb carbon dioxide and store carbon in their sediments, thereby lessening the impacts of global warming; and help in the protection of associated marine ecosystems. Provides food, fuel, fodder and a host of other useful products. Mangrove and estuaries are the breeding ground for many estuarine species and nursery ground for many marine species. Many birds also find their habitat in mangrove forests. Mangrove Forests are largely facing deforestation.

Livestock

Management strategy:

- a. Grazing land for livestock will be arranged. Facilities for livestock development will be enhanced;
- b. Facilities for rearing of poultry of different species including the local ones will be enhanced.

Afforestation

Management strategy:

- a. Measures will be taken for afforestation in the coastal areas including newly accreted chars;
- b. Effective measures will be taken for conservation of forests;
- c. Social forestry will be encouraged and extended.

Water

Addressing Water Related Issues that Need Immediate Action

- Water and ecosystem management zones and community participation
- Supply of domestic water and mitigation of arsenic contamination
- Equitable allocation of multi-purpose shelters
- Rationalization of flood control polders
- Augmentation of inflow to the Ganges distributary by basin wide management

Management strategy:

- a. Adequate upland flow shall be ensured in water channels to preserve the coastal estuary ecosystem threatened by the intrusion of soil salinity from the sea;
- b. Small water reservoirs shall be built to capture tidal water in order to enhance minor irrigation in coastal areas. Appropriate water management system within the polder utilizing existing infrastructures will be established for freshwater storage and other water utilization;
- c. Rainwater harvesting and conservation shall be promoted;

- d. Ponds and tanks will be excavated for conservation of water and local technology for water
- e. treatment will be used for the supply of safe water;
- f. Step will be taken to ensure sustainable use and management of ground water.

Aquaculture

Management strategy:

- a. Environmentally adopted and socially responsive shrimp farming will be encouraged. In this regard, internationally accepted quality control measures will be introduced;
- b. All opportunities and potentials of aquaculture will be utilized in the coastal zone. Crab culture, pearl culture, sea grass will be encouraged.

Tourism

Tourism is recognized as an industry with multidimensional aspects. Co-ordinate involvement of many sectoral agencies is vital for the growth of this industry. Coastal beaches, among others, are considered as one of the attractions. Cox's Bazar- the longest beach of the world, Sundarban- the largest mangrove forest of the world and St'Martins island- the coral reef island of Bangladesh is the most tourism potential coastal zones. Following management plan should be taken in consideration-

- a. Encouragement of domestic and foreign investments in the private sector to promote tourism;
- b. Development of the rich cultural, historical and religious pasts of tourist sites along with providing modern facilities for foreign tourists;
- c. Development of facilities to encourage domestic tourism;
- d. Development of tourism facilities in Cox's Bazar sea beach;
- e. Development of Kuakata and sea beaches in southern Bangladesh;

Habitat Degradation and Migration

Habitat degradation is one of the devastating consequences of natural disasters like river erosion, cyclones, flood, storm surges and like these activities. Cyclone Aila, 2009 and its consequences is a great evidence of habitat degradation. As a result people migrated from the affected areas to other areas for their existence and livelihoods (Mallick *et al.*, 2012). Agricultural crop failure due to natural hazards like flood causes displacement of human from one place to another. Climate change induced disasters also causes long term population displacement from rural areas to another places (Gray *et al.*, 2012). People lost their houses and to find income generating activities was very much difficult after cyclone Aila. People then depended on the relief which were provided by different GOs and NGOs. After the end of the relief giving activities people had to move to the nearby districts for their livelihoods.

Then migration or population displacement had started severely from southwest coastal region due to the destructive activities of cyclone (Mallick *et al.* 2013).

Possible Management activities:

- a. Encouraging household's plinth raise activities
- b. Providing facilities for building strong houses
- c. Encouraging cultivating saline tolerant rice varieties
- d. Building awareness about adaptation activities
- e. Providing alternative livelihoods to the affected areas.

Sustainable management of natural resources

Coastal zone is full of diverse natural resources: inland fisheries & shrimp, marine fisheries, mangrove and other forests, land, livestock, salt, minerals, sources of renewable energy like tide, wind and solar energy. Medium and long term Government policy to ensure sustainable management of both biotic and abiotic coastal resources will be as follows:

Every possible step shall be taken to secure just share from all international rivers reaching the coastal zone and the Bay of Bengal;

- a. Suitable measures will be taken for sustainable use of renewable resources and, to that end, limit harvesting, extraction or utilization to the corresponding cycles of their regeneration;
- b. Sustainable use of coastal resources shall be ensured. Combination of resource use, e.g. agriculture, forestry and fishing including aquaculture is often the major economic activity. Efforts will be given to make this sustainable;
- c. Optimum utilization of resources will be ensured by taking advantage of the complementarities and trade-offs between competing uses;
- d. Rigid enforcement of conservation regulations will affect the livelihoods of many people and such conservation efforts will be linked, as far as possible, with alternative opportunities of employment;
- e. Initiation of plan and its implementation will be ensured by participation of people of all sectors.

Societal Impacts and Governance

Major impacts of climate change on the coastal

Due to diverse economic activities (mainly burning of fossil fuel), carbon dioxide (CO₂) and other greenhouse gases (methane, nitrous oxide, ozone, chlorofluorocarbons and water vapor) are accumulated in the earth's atmosphere, resulting in climate change. Rising temperature expand the ocean volume in two ways. Firstly, it melts mass volume of ice of the polar region and secondly, it causes thermal expansion of water of the ocean (L.Hossain & k.Hossain

2005). Ongoing climate has a greater socio economic and environmental impact on different countries. Bangladesh is considered as one of the most vulnerable countries due to climate change. Among the adverse effect of climate change, it is evident that Sea level rise is the major concern for Bangladesh which can bring a higher cost for the entire economy of this country which is difficult to capture in monetary term also. In this study the exertion is given to analyze the ongoing and long run effect of sea level rise in the coastal areas of Bangladesh. It deserves special mention that the affected districts those who are impacting by the sea level rise will spread out the cost in entire economy in the form of climate migration in cities, regional food insecurity, and poverty.

There are environmental, non-environmental, economic, non-economic, social, tangible, and intangible various kind impact of climate change. For better and precise analysis we categorized the impact into three parts. These are Biotic impact, Abiotic impact, and Socio-economic impact.

Biotic Stress:

The human activities those who are affected by changing climate are fall into biotic stress. The Impact directly affect the Human activities are discussed here. These are,

Agriculture:

Salinity intrusion due to sea level rise will decrease agricultural production by unavailability of fresh water and soil fertility. Salinity also decreases the terminative energy and germination rate of some plants (Rashid et al., 2004). Ali (2005) investigated the loss of rice production in a village of Satkhira district and found that rice production in 2003 was 1,151 metric tons less than the year 1985.

Health

Sea level rise may increase the risk of health hazards like diarrhea, cholera, etc. Cholera is an infectious disease of the small intestine of human beings and is common in the coastal area of Bangladesh. Water salinity and its distribution in the coastal area are increasing with the increase of sea level rise (Faisal and Parveen, 2004; IPCC, 2001a; World Bank, 2000). With the increased density and distribution of salinity, cholera germs are getting favorable habitat and spreading in the coastal area. This hypothesis is also supported by Colwell and Huq (2001) that states, most major epidemics that have occurred during the last 50 years originated in coastal region. So, coastal water and its saline environment have close association with cholera disease. Outbreaks of cholera often occur after flooding. Besides, due to SLR the natural disaster becomes more frequent which may bring various unknown disease in future.

Tourism

A significant part of Bangladesh coast is sandy beaches that attract tourists. Kuakata beach in Patuakhali district, Patenga beach in Chittagong district and Cox's Bazar beach in Cox's Bazar district are attractive tourist areas of the country. Out of 18 most lucrative tourist areas identified by Bangladesh Parjatan Corporation, five spots namely Chittagong, Cox's Bazar, Kuakata, Khulna and the Sundarbans are located in the coastal zone are in extreme risk to destroy by SLR.

Abiotic Stress:

In abiotic stress the Impact directly affect the environment and ecosystem are discussed. These are under mentioned.

Frequent Natural Disaster

Experts explain that rising sea levels will cause water to mix with sea water, thereby making once potable freshwater drinking sources no longer available for human consumption. Moreover, rising sea levels has also been linked to other devastating side effects, such as an increase in earthquakes and other major seismic events. Other drastic weather events that can happen because of melting polar ice caps and glaciers and rising sea levels include an increase in the number of landslides and tsunamis felt around the world. Recently a number of natural disaster has taken place in Bangladesh such as Sidr, Aila, and Nargis.

Monsoon flooding

Under climate change scenario about 18 per cent of current lowly flooded areas will be susceptible to higher levels of flooding while about 12 to 16 per cent new areas will be at risk of varied degrees of inundation. As per NAPA recommendations, SLRs in the coast of Bangladesh are 14 cm, 32 cm and 88 cm for the year 2030, 2050 and 2100. In a recent study, IWM (2006) predicted that flooding of coastal lands may increase by 21% by the year 2001 while it is 10.3% for the year 2050 with respect to ordinary flooding condition when approximately 50% lands go under flood.

Reduction of Agriculture Land

According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, Bangladesh is slated to lose the largest amount of cultivated land due to rising sea levels. A 1 meter rise in sea levels would inundate 20 percent of the country's landmass. Reduction of agriculture land is a vast problem for the local people and they are suffering much for the cause.

Decline in Soil Quality

Due to sea level rise salinity intrusion causes decline in soil quality. The soil profile of the affected area is totally changing and this situation led to unproductive land. The soil profile is also changing which has a devastating effect on coastal areas.

Species Disappearing

It is predicted that sea level rise can cause to destroy the forest, land, fresh water resource, and living environment of coastal areas. As a result some species may extinct in the coastal zone. Furthermore, species extinction may lead to destroy the traditional biodiversity in the coastal areas of Bangladesh which has a greater environmental cost.

Coastal Erosion

The major factors of coastal erosion in Bangladesh include Strong tidal action and storm surges, High wind waves and current during monsoon, and High river discharge (central coastal zone). There are no accurate measurements on coastal erosion due to SLR. However, many researchers estimated the potential impacts of SLR on erosions. For example, Islam et al. (1999) predicted that average recession of the eastern coastline of Bangladesh would be about 87 times the SLR. If that is true then the land loss is:

- 6.26 sq. km for SLR of 0.1 m
- 18.79 sq. km for SLR of 0.3 m
- 62.64 sq. km for SLR of 1.0 m

Water Logging

The problem of water logging was first started during 1960 after the construction of coastal polders (dikes) with sluice gates controlling river flows and to protect low-lying agricultural lands from tidal inundation and saline water intrusion. After the construction of polders, the silt was deposited on the river beds, resulting in the silting up of rivers. Eventually, the exit points of the sluice gates became blocked, and subsequently, the emboldened areas became permanently water logged.

Socio-Economic Impact of Sea Level Rise

In this part the environmental impact of climate change has been evaluated from the Socio-economic perspective. Here emphasize is given to scrutinize the socio economic vulnerabilities of coastal areas of Bangladesh due to environmental impact of SLR. There are nineteen coastal districts in Bangladesh which are on high risky position in terms of socio economic vulnerability due to the changing climate. According to BBS, there are 35.1 million people are living in the coastal areas are Bangladesh which are counted as 28 percent of total population size of the country. The economic activities of coastal zone are circulated by fishing, agriculture, salt farming and shrimp cultivation. These economic activities are fully dependent on natural resources and environmental sustainability. Any changes in

environmental behavior can bring a significant impact on coastal economy and its players. In this section the socio economic parameters of coastal zone that can be affected by the Sea level rise has been highlighted for economic analysis.

Unemployment

Unemployment will be the crucial outcome of Sea level rise in the coastal areas of Bangladesh. According to IPCC (2009), sea level has rising for last 30 years at an average rate of 5 millimeters per year In Bangladesh. After few years rising trend of sea level will triumph over the sea side land and salinity attack the agricultural land and fresh water. Consequently, agricultural production, fishing, and salt farming will be hampered drastically. As a penalty, people those who are relying on this type of economic activities will be unemployed. The socio economic cost of this sort of climate pinned unemployment is higher.

Infrastructure Destruction

There are 35,712 kilometers established roads in the coastal zone (Sarwar, 05). Every year natural disaster causes to destroy a tremendous part of roads. Besides, bridge, culvert, embankment are also harmed. Repairing and reconstruction cost of this sort of infrastructure is high. Sea side ship-breaking industries, tourist spot, public & private infrastructure will also be damaged due to sea level rise. Our most important tourist attraction Cox's bazaar, Kuakata, St. Martin, Sundarbans will be adversely affected by the sea level rise. Near future tourist business will lose revenue from these areas. The people those who are employed in tourist sector in the coastal zone will be in risk on massive job lose.

Emergence of Climate Refugee

According to IPCC 1 meter rise in sea level will lead to go down most of the part of southern and western region of Bangladesh under water. As a result 30 million people from southern and western part of Bangladesh will be deadly affected. They will lose their land and living place. More than 20 million people will be climate refugee due to sea level rise (khan, 07). These people will create chaos in the city and city may not properly accommodate this huge amount of displaced people.

High Cost of Natural Disasters

There is a significant socio-economic cost of natural disaster caused by sea level rise. According to weather dept. of Bangladesh, during 1990 to 2004 every year 10 cyclone hits the coastal area of Bangladesh. But in 2006 16 cyclones hits Bangladesh and in 2008 it stands to 20 after 2020 cyclone will hit more rapidly and the cost of damage of life, asset, environment, plant, animal will be sky high.

Loss of GDP and Emergence of Macroeconomic Tension

According to IPCC just 1 meter rise in sea level will cause to go down 22000 square kilometers land under water which is 16% of our total land area. In this circumstance we will lose our agricultural and industrial production from these areas. According to WB, 1 meter rise in sea level will lead to reduce the rice production by half. Which estimated cost in current market price is \$3.5 billion. This consequence will triggered food inflation and food insecurity in the economy. According to MoE, for the consequences of climate change right now we are losing 1.81% GDP annually after 2030 we will lose more than 2.5 percent of our GDP. This sort of economic loss will cause to emerge macroeconomic stress.

Risk on Education System

Due to change in climate natural disaster i.e tsunami, cyclone, flood, tidal upsurge, water logging will be frequent. As a result educational institutions near to coastal area get flooded or ruined and remain closed until reconstruction. Most of the time educational institution those are not affected by natural disaster and these are turned into shelter place for the affected people. Furthermore, due to natural calamity affected students are unable to attend classes. Consequently, education system collapse in coastal area. On the other hand natural disaster breaks up social safe net of affected region. People become poor. Death toll of earning person of a household by the natural disaster bound student to do work for survival, which lead termination of education life of a child. This situation will be more deepen in future when natural disaster will be more frequent and huge amount of land will go under water by the sea level rise. So in upcoming time education system will be hampered magnificently in coastal reason. This will imply higher level of socio-economic cost.

Appearance of Climate Poverty

As we know due to sea level rise 19 districts of Bangladesh will go under water (IPCC). As a result people will lose their resources. Farmer, fisherman, salt producer will lose their profession and earning source. a large number of people will not find any suitable work. Some of them will choose to work in informal sector to survive. There are about 6.8 million households in the coastal zone of which 52 percent are absolute poor (Islam, 2004).

High Economic Cost of Loosing Natural Resources

Due to sea level rise we will lose our environmentally and economically valuable forest resources. Forest maintains the ecological balance and also a rich source of firewood, lumber, paper, foodstuff, and raw materials of different industry. According to the prediction of WB (2000) by 2020 Sundarbans will inundates 15% and by 2050 it will Inundates 40% and by 2100 whole Sundarbans will be lost due to sea level rise. Here it is noted that the Sundarbans is a major earning source of 10 million subsistence people (Islam & Haque, 2004). People those who rely on Sundarbans will be vulnerable and we will also loose forest products. On

the other hand to meet the local demand we have to import forest product from abroad by the cost of foreign reserve. So both in the short run and long run the socio-economic cost of loosing natural resources is sky high due to SLR. Moreover, sea level rise will also ruin the rangeland. As a result the supply of beef, mutton, milk, vegetable will be decline considerably. Consequently, people of coastal areas will get less protein which may lead hard core food poverty (According to WFP, per capita calorie consumption less than 1805 kilo calorie per day is categorized as a hardcore poverty).

Diminution of Social Welfare

Climate change will cause to disrupt the basic needs of coastal people i.e. Food, Cloths, Housing, Health, and Education. Poor people will be more vulnerable and social safety net will be break down of the affected areas. Hence, the social welfare of the people will be trimmed down. All the socio economic cost of SLR cannot be monetized due to methodology constraint but the welfare diminution of the people of coastal area will adversely affect the overall human development process of the country.

Future Impacts and Vulnerabilities Due to Climate Change

The impacts of climate change are not restricted to sea-level rise. The most profound impacts will be in agriculture and food security, water, biodiversity changes, human health and human migration. The reductions in yields of staple crops such as rice and wheat are anticipated to be huge: by 2050 rice yield could to drop by 8% and wheat yield by 32%.

The IPCC identify South Asia as having the highest proportion of ‘highly vulnerable’ sectors of all the Asia sub-regions, with food, biodiversity, water, coastal ecosystems, human health and land degradation all judged to be ‘highly vulnerable’ to the impacts of climate change. Bangladesh’s National Adaptation Program of Action (NAPA) provides more detail about the most vulnerable sectors and localities in Bangladesh, reproduced below:

Table 6: Most vulnerable sectors and localities in Bangladesh

Climate and Related factors	Most Vulnerable Areas	Highest Impact Sectors
Temperature rise and drought	North West	Agriculture, Water, Health, Energy
Sea level rise and	Coastal area Islands	Agriculture (crop, fisheries, livestock), Water (Water logging, drinking water), Human Settlement, Energy, Health
Floods	Central region North east region Char lands	Agriculture (crop, fisheries, livestock), Water (urban, industry), Infrastructure,

		Human settlement, Health, Disaster, Energy
Cyclone and storm surge	Coastal and marine areas	Marine fishing, Infrastructure, Human settlement, Life and property
Drainage congestion	Coastal area Urban South west	Agriculture (crop), Water (navigation)

Adaptation Measures to mitigate the impacts of climate change

Climate change is currently causing increased hardship for rural communities throughout Bangladesh. Moreover, current global levels of greenhouse gas pollution means that the impacts of climate change are now set to worsen over the coming decades regardless of future emissions. However, whilst the most profound impacts of climate change may still be some years away, our understanding of future climate scenarios means that actions to help prepare communities can be taken now. Importantly, strategies that build community’s ability to adapt to climate change can and must be undertaken now: it will be too late to act once the last crops have failed or glacial lakes have burst.

Strategies for adaptation need to focus on the needs of the people most affected by climate change impacts and aim to reduce the most significant hazards they face. Identifying communities’ own priorities and needs and valuing their knowledge alongside science-based knowledge is key to developing sound adaptation strategies. Sharing experiences, obstacles and positive initiatives with other communities and development policy-makers must be an integral part of national adaptation strategies. The primary role of governments and international processes is in developing and implementing policy that is enabling for local-level action.

However, some important adaptation activities, such as management of increasingly scarce or flood prone water resources, will require coordination at the regional and intergovernmental levels. Development of adaptation strategies at the national level is underway in some Least Developed Countries, including Bangladesh, where National Adaptation Programs of Action (NAPAs) identify priorities for adaptation projects. To ensure a positive impact on the most vulnerable communities, climate change adaptation should support the development of community based systems of adaptation. These should be based on sustainable livelihood options and sound management of ecosystems through strengthening capacities, skills and institutions to react and adapt to climate generated changes. More specifically, climate change adaptation strategies, including the NAPAs, should:

- Begin with vulnerability assessments based on strong gender analysis to focus on the most vulnerable and their needs within the communities and to identify and reduce the most significant vulnerabilities they face.

- Value the knowledge and strategies that the poor are already using to cope with climate change and use this as a basis to identify priorities and define action.
- Empower communities to participate in the development of climate change sensitive interventions and policies, ensuring effective interaction between decision-makers and planners from key climate change affected sectors in both government and donors' structures.
- Require agriculture, energy, transport and health departments of Government to undertake an analysis of predicted climate change and how it will impact on their sector.
- Facilitate delivery of resources, support and services to community level, including information, skills, technology, finance and basic services and activities aimed at Disaster Risk Reduction.
- Ensure that risks related to climate change and community-based responses to adaptation are mainstreamed into the most appropriate planning frameworks and development plans (including PRSPs).

Potential adaptation strategies exist for all sectors and can be implemented as community based adaptation projects:

Agriculture sector

- Diversification of crop agriculture is a key approach in addressing climate change, but requires research on appropriate varieties for the new physical, social and climatic conditions. Diversification should be coupled with the revitalization of local varieties that have a greater resilience to extreme climate events.
- Household and community assets can be reinforced through alternative livelihood options such as homestead gardening, horticulture, floating gardens and handicraft production. Increasing assets and diversifying livelihood options are key components in ensuring that communities are able to adapt to meet the challenges that climate change brings.
- Information on pest control and methods to protect winter vegetables from extreme cold and fog needs to be disseminated.
- Seed banks can be established to ensure that varieties remain available following disaster periods.
- Awareness raising on strategies for building adaptive capacity and the implications of climate change amongst local level non-government organizations, agricultural extension officers, block supervisor of Department of Agricultural Extension (DAE), and farmers.

Housing and settlement

- Flood risk can be alleviated through building raised house plinths for the homes of affected people.
- Homestead plantations can protect settlements from flood and erosion.
- Raising water pumps so that flood water does not contaminate drinking water.

Rivers

- Dredging of river beds combats increased sedimentation, thereby improving navigability.
- Increasing vegetative coverage along river banks protects against erosion resulting from increased flow and flooding.

Awareness raising and capacity building

Mass awareness rising on the impacts of climate change and how to cope with the challenges can be carried out through a variety of means, such as the distribution of posters or leaflets, running discussion sessions with different groups such as NGOs, Upazila level officials (agriculture, disaster management unit), or setting up school and college environmental clubs that can arrange discussions on local issues.

Community based adaptation also emphasizes the need for communities to understand that climate change means that traditional responses to climate variation may no longer be sufficient when long term shifts in temperature and rainfall are predicted. Women, who frequently manage local natural resources, are central to ensuring that the impacts of climate change are properly understood. By building on their understanding of the climate and their environment, and by sharing their experiences with others, communities are able to develop their own strategies for climate change adaptation. Local and national government policy is therefore needed to support the communities in this process of defining and achieving their own goals.

Recommendations for Policy Makers

Policy makers from all sectors urgently need to focus attention on the implications of climate change. Support for adaptation to the impacts must start now. Many aspects of climate change and variability are already having a profound effect on the livelihoods of poor rural communities and enough is known about the future impacts of climate change for action to be taken now. The vulnerability of the poorest to climate change is a central challenge. ‘No regrets’ adaptation options, which focus on poverty relief through diversifying livelihoods and extension support for sustainable agricultural systems, must be a priority.

In particular, action is required in the following areas:

Central government

Impact

- Climate change is not just an issue for those in government with responsibility for the environment.

Recommendations

- All government departments must acknowledge the importance of climate change and analyze the impacts for their sector. Disaster planning and risk reduction strategies must account for the new challenges of climate induced disasters.
- Central government will need to support decentralized policy development so that appropriate adaptation activities can be planned and prevent the imposition of ‘one size fits all’ solutions. National level activities need to support the distribution of resources and extension services to the local level, training and awareness-raising in communities, research for technology generation, information provision, and take forward international lobbying.

Coastal and river zones

Impacts

- 1 million people are expected to be affected by sea level rise in the region of the Ganges-Brahmaputra-Meghna mega delta by 2050.
- Sea level rise leading to saline water intrusion, coastal land inundation and storm surges are unavoidable.

Recommendations

- Policy makers must start planning now to protect the infrastructure and settlements of the rural poor in the region of the Ganges-Brahmaputra-Meghna mega delta and identify whether mass migration can be avoided.
- The implications of sea level rise are profound and must be prepared for in the areas of government responsible for agriculture, trade, population planning, disaster preparedness, the environment and finance.
- Government should explore methods for construction of embankments to protect communities from saline water intrusion and tidal surge. Communities should be involved in routine maintenance of embankments. In addition, support should be given to farmers to cultivate saline tolerant paddy.

Agricultural and fishery policy and extension support

Impacts

- Huge reductions in the levels of rice and wheat production are anticipated in the coming years. Estimates suggest that rice production could fall by 8% and wheat production by 32% by as early as 2050. Fish stocks are already reported to be in decline due to early flooding, temperature fluctuations and river bed siltation.
- Increased water stress is expected by 2020 and will have a huge impact on the productivity and viability of irrigation fed agriculture.

Recommendations

Government should provide support to farmers in their use of alternative technologies in the agriculture sector. Strategies such as floating gardens, fish cultivation cages, adjustments to

the cropping calendar, flood tolerant paddy cultivation, plus alternative crops and livestock that are resilient to climate change (and higher winter temperatures in particular) should all be promoted.

Health

Impacts

- Water supply, food security and land degradation or inundation will all place pressures on rural populations that will lead to deteriorating health in, and reduced viability of, existing rural population centres.
- Flooding and sea level rise will lead to the pollution of surface water, an increase in water borne diseases such as cholera and an escalation of current high rates of diarrhoea.

Recommendations

- Specific health and sanitation measures will need to complement alternative livelihood strategies if a widespread deterioration in health is to be avoided.
- The impact of the government plan for sanitation in all villages initiative should be maximized by inviting NGOs to create awareness in the communities. Existing community clinics need to be fully operational and the necessary logistical support ensured to meet the challenges that climate change presents.

Conclusion

The Bay of Bengal has been increasingly important for local development as well as for a global perspective. Due to the geographical position and climatic condition, the coastal area of the country is known as one of the highly productive areas of the world. The biological and ecological values of the Bay of Bengal have been pointed out by many authors. The Bay of Bengal and its coastal areas is one of the least scientific explored areas of the world ocean although the oceanic features are quite diverse. Marine stock enhancement and sea ranching are yet to be developed for the Bay. Proper attention is needed in every aspect of research and development.

References

- Ahmed, A. (2011). Some of the major environmental problems relating to land use changes in the coastal areas of Bangladesh: A review. *Journal of Geography and Regional Planning* Vol. 4(1), pp. 1-8.
- Ali A (1979) Storm Surges in the Bay of Bengal and Some Related Problems. Ph.D. Thesis, University Of Reading, England, 227 pp.
- Brown, J.E.M. (2005) “Generating river discharge estimates for the Bay of Bengal using the NASA GSFC Land Information System”, Rosenstein School of Marine and Atmospheric Science (RSMAS), University of Miami
- Choudhury, J.U. (2011) Issues in Coastal Zone Management in Bangladesh, http://teacher.buet.ac.bd/msalamkhan/teaching_msk_files/coastal_issues_bd.pdf (accessed in October 2014)
- Debsarma, Sujit Kumar (2009), “Simulation of Storm Surges in the Bay of Bengal”, *Marine Geodesy*, 32:2, 178-198 psp.
- FAO. (1989). Arid zone forestry: a guide for field technicians. FAO Conservation Guide No. 20. 143 pp.
- Golledge N. R., Menviel L., Carter L., Fogwill C. J., England M. H., Cortese G., Levy R. H.. (2014) Antarctic contribution to meltwater pulse 1A from reduced Southern Ocean overturning. *Nature Communications*,; 5: 5107 DOI:10.1038/ncomms6107
- Gönnert G, Dube SK, Murty T, Siefert W. Global storm surges. *Die Küste* 2001. 63, p 623
- Gray, C. L. and Mueller, V. (2012). Natural disasters and population mobility in Bangladesh. *Proc Natl Acad Sci USA* 109(16):6000–6005. doi:10.1073/pnas.1115944109
- Hassan, S.M. Q. (2005). Storm Surge Prediction and Inundation Along Bangladesh Coast Using Satellite Data and Model. Pilot Project Report of Centre for Space Science and Technology Education, Asia and the Pacific (CSSTE-AP). Ahmedabad, India.
- Hossain, M.S., Lin, C.K., Tokunaga, M., Demaine, H., and Hussain, M.Z. (2003). Land use zoning for solar salt production in Cox’s Bazar coast of Bangladesh: A Remote Sensing and GIS analysis. *Asian Journal of Geoinformatics*.
- IPCC, (2007). *Climate Change 2007: The Physical Science Basis*. Contribution of Working Group I to the Fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [Solomon, S., D. Qin, M. Manning, Z. Chen, M. Marquis, K.B. Averyt, M. Tignor and H.L. Miller (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, 996 pp
- J. Fasullo, and PJ Webster. (2003). A Hydrological Definition of Indian Monsoon Onset and Withdrawal. *Journa of Climate*, Vol.1
- Jevrejeva S, Grinsted A, MoorJ C e (2014). Upper limit for sea level projections by 2100. *Environmental Research Letters*,; 9 (10): 104008 DOI: 10.1088/1748-9326/9/10/104008
- Joseph P. V., 2011, “Onset, Advance and Withdrawal of Monsoon”, Monsoon Monograph, Ed. Asnani et al, India Meteorological Department, N. Delhi, Vol. 1, 554pp
- Joseph, P. V. (2014). Role of Ocean in the Variability of Indian Summer Monsoon Rainfall. *Surveys Geophysics*, 35:723–738, DOI 10.1007/s10712-013-9274-7
- Joseph, P. V., G. Bindu, A. Nair, et al., (2013). Variability of summer monsoon rainfall in India on inter-annual and decadal time scales, *Atmos. Oceanic Sci.Lett.* , 6 , 398– 403, doi:10.3878/j.issn.1674-2834.13.0044.
- Katharine Grant, (2014) Eelco Rohling. Sea-level variability over five glacial cycles. *Nature Communications*, DOI: 10.1038/ncomm6076

- Khan, M.G., M. Humayun, M.G. Mustafa, B. Mansura, S.C. Paul and M.N.U. Sada. (1983). Results from the 15th cruise (December 1983) of the R.V. Anusandhani to the demersal fishing grounds of the northern Bay of Bengal 8 p. (mimeo).
- Kumar, S. P., Sardesai, S., Ramaiah, N., Bhosle, N.B., Ramaswamy, V., Ramesh, R., Sharada, M.K., Sarin, M.M., Sarupriya, J.S. and Muraleedharan, U. (2006) Final Report Submitted to the Department of Ocean Development New Delhi, Bay of Bengal Process Studies.
- Lamboeuf, M. (1987). Bangladesh demersal fish resources of the continental shelf. R.V. Anusandhani trawling survey results (Sep. 1984 - June, 1986) Rep. Prep. for the FAO/UNDP project strengthening of the national program for Marine Fish Resources Management Research and Development. FAO, Rome, 1987, FI: DP/BGD/80/025, Field document 1: 26 p.
- Mallick, B. and Vogt, J. (2012). Cyclone, coastal society and migration: empirical evidence from Bangladesh. *International Development Planning Review*, 34 (3) 2012
doi:10.3828/idpr.2012.16
- Mallick, B. and Vogt, J. (2013). Population displacement after cyclone and its consequences: empirical evidence from coastal Bangladesh. *Nat Hazards* DOI 10.1007/s11069-013-0803-y
- Md Mizanur Rahman, M Rafiuddin and Md Mahbub Alam, (2010). Seasonal forecasting of Bangladesh summer monsoon rainfall using simple multiple regression model.
- Nidheesh, A.G., Lengaigne, M., Vialard, J., Unnikrishnan, A.S., Dayan, H., (2013). Decadal and long-term sea level variability in the tropical Indo-Pacific Ocean, *Climate Dynamics*, vol.41; 2013; 381-402
- Penn, J.W. (1983). An assessment of potential yield from the offshore demersal shrimp and fish stock in Bangladesh water (including comments on the trawl fishery 1981-1982). FE:DP/BGD/81. 634, Field Doc. 22 p. Fishery Advisory Service (Phase II) Project, FAO, Rome, Italy.
- Quader, O (2010). Coastal and marine biodiversity of Bay of Bengal (Bangladesh). Proc. of International Conference on Environmental Aspects of Bangladesh (ICEAB10), Japan,
- Rahman, M M. (2006). A validation of regional climate model simulation with observational data over Bangladesh, M. Phil thesis, Bangladesh University of Engineering and Technology (BUET)
- Reeve, M.S. Syed, M.A. Spengler, T and Spinney, J. 2014. Complementing Scientific Monsoon Definitions with Social perceptions in Bangladesh, *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society (BAMS)*, June 2, 2014, <http://journals.ametsoc.org/doi/pdf/10.1175/BAMS-D-13-00144.1>
- Rye, Craig D.; Naveira Garabato, Alberto C.; Holland, Paul R.; Meredith, Michael P.; Nurser, A.J. George; Hughes, Chris W.; Coward, Andrew C.; Webb, David J.. (2014) Rapid sea-level rise along the Antarctic margins in response to increased glacial discharge. *Nature Geoscience*, 7 (10). 732-735 10.1038/ngeo2230
- Saetre, R. (1981). Survey of the marine fish resources of Bangladesh Nov.-Dec. 1979 and May 1980. Report on surveys in the R.V. Dr. Fridtj of Nansen. Institute of Marine Research, Bergen. 67 p.
- Sarkar, Nikhil Chandra (2012) A Numerical Simulation of Severe Cyclone Sidr-2007 Ganit J. Bangladesh Math. Soc. (ISSN 1606-3694) 32, 43-54pp.
- Storch, Hans von 2012. Storm Surges: Phenomena, Forecasting and Scenarios of Change, *Procedia IUTAM 00 (2012) 000–000*, Science Direct, Elsevier
- Varadachari, V.V.R., Murry, C.S., and Reddy C.V.G. (1968) "Salinity maxima associated with some subsurface water masses in the upper layers of the Bay of Bengal", *Bulletin of the National Institute of Oceanography*, 38,338-343.
- White, T.F. and M.G. Khan. (1985) The marine fishery resources of Bangladesh and their potential for commercial development. Key note paper, In: Proc. of the National Seminar on Fisheries Development in Bangladesh, BFDC, MoFL, Dhaka. January 1985. 4 p.

Zhu J.-J. (2008). Wind Shelterbelts. *Encyclopedia of Ecology*, 2008, Pages 3803-3812